

Rock power: Geothermal power simulations for schools

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Earth Learning Idea is a web-based, global teaching resource. It provides freely-downloadable activities for teachers of science, geography and related subjects. All are written in the same format, with the activity described first, followed by full teacher back-up, including context, pupil learning outcomes, underlying principles and thinking skills. The activity described here models geothermal power sources and challenges pupils to say whether they are renewable or not. The apparatus, involving a density can and gravel, is simple to assemble and can be used to simulate 'hot dry rocks', 'hot wet rocks' and hydrothermal power. Ground source heat pumps are also discussed. The statement, found in many science textbooks, that 'geothermal energy is renewable' is debated.

"Earth Learning Idea" ou le concept d'éducation en Géosciences représente une ressource globale d'enseignement avec support numérique (web). Il fournit gratuitement des sujets d'activité téléchargeables à l'intention de professeurs de sciences, de géographie et de thèmes associés. Les sujets sont tous écrits avec le même format, le type d'activité décrit en premier, suivi du soutien et du contrôle du professeur concerné, incluant le contexte, ce qu'a retenu l'élève, en soulignant les principes et les manières de penser. Le sujet décrit ici représente les différents modèles d'énergie géothermique et teste les élèves pour savoir s'il s'agit d'énergies renouvelables ou pas. Le dispositif, impliquant un densitomètre et du gravier, est simple à assembler et peut servir à simuler l'effet de roches chaudes, sèches ou humides et d'énergie hydrothermale. Les pompes à chaleur air-eau sont également étudiées. L'affirmation, rencontrée dans nombre de manuels scientifiques selon laquelle l'énergie géothermique est renouvelable, fait partie du débat.

"Earth Learning Idea" es un recurso de enseñanza global basado en la web. Proporciona actividades que se pueden descargar de forma gratuita para profesores de ciencias, geografía y temas relacionados. Todos están escritos en el mismo formato, en primer lugar se describe la actividad, el profesor tiene un apoyo completo incluyendo el contexto de la actividad, los resultados del aprendizaje por parte del alumno, los principios subyacentes y las habilidades de pensamiento. La actividad descrita aquí modela fuentes de energía geotérmica y desafía a los alumnos a decir si son renovables o no. El aparato, que implica una capa de densidad y grava, es fácil de montar y puede ser usado para simular 'rocas calientes secas', 'rocas calientes húmedas' y energía hidrotérmica. También se discuten las bombas de calor. Se debate la declaración que se encuentra en muchos manuales de ciencias, según la que "la energía geotérmica es renovable".

Earth Learning Idea, accessible at <http://www.earthlearningidea.com/>, was set up in May 2007, for the International Year of Planet Earth, with the intention of reaching as many children throughout the world as possible, particularly those who suffer from lack of resources and from lack of thought-provoking teaching. The aim is to foster a better knowledge of the natural world and how it works, encouraging the joy of knowledge about the Earth in those who may not otherwise have the opportunity to receive it.

Earth Learning Idea publishes a new Earth science teaching activity every two weeks. By the end of 2016, 251 activities had been published in English and another

20 activities were in preparation. All are written in the same format, with the activity described first, followed by comprehensive teaching notes, including context, pupil learning outcomes, underlying principles and thinking skills. All activities are made available as free-to-download pdf files with a download rate of more than 40,000 per month and the total number of downloads approaching 3 million (King, 2017; King *et al.*, 2007, 2010, 2013, 2014). The website carries, or links to, more than 820 translations of activities, facilitated through a voluntary collaborative global network. The translations are chiefly in Spanish, Catalan, Portuguese, Norwegian, Italian, Japanese and German, but also in Polish, Slovakian and South Korean. We are hugely grateful for the efforts of our colleagues around the world in translating all these Earth Learning Ideas.

The activity below describes an edited version of just one of the 250+ Earth Learn-

ing Idea activities – focussed, in this case, on geothermal power.

Rock power: geothermal power simulations

Modelling geothermal power sources – renewable or not?

Add water to a heated gravel-filled density can, to model three types of geothermal power source, like this:

Fill the density can with coarse permeable gravel and carefully insert a vertical Pyrex™ tube until it nearly reaches the bottom, as shown in the diagram, *Figure 1*.

Then heat the apparatus up in an oven or on a hot plate (e.g. to 100 °C); be aware of the safety risk from the hot can. Once hot, add a thermometer or temperature probe to the top of the gravel, and get a container

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Figure 1: The apparatus (photo courtesy of Chris King).

ready with a thermometer to catch overflowing water and measure its temperature.

Then use this apparatus to model the following forms of geothermal power source, (see Figure 2).

'Hot dry rocks'

Model this by adding water steadily to the Pyrex™ tube and catching the overflow, whilst monitoring the temperature of the gravel and overflow water. 'Hot dry rocks' are rocks like granite that have become warm over millions of years of decay of the radioactive minerals they contain. The heat can be extracted by drilling two bore-holes into the granite, ensuring these are connected by cracks, then pumping water around the system.

'Hot wet rocks'

Simulate this as described above, but first, fill the hot can with water until it just overflows, then leave it for some time (e.g. 5 minutes). This models how water trapped in deep permeable rocks (aquifers) that are insulated by thick sequences of overlying rocks, can accumulate geothermal heat. 'Extract' the heat by adding water to the Pyrex™ tube, as above, monitoring the gravel and overflow water temperatures.

'Hydrothermal power'

To model this, stand the density can on a hot plate and repeat the activity. Hydrothermal power is extracted where there is a source of geothermal heat near the Earth's surface, as found in places like Iceland, Italy, Japan, New Zealand and the Yellowstone area of the USA. 'Extract' the heat from the model by adding water down the Pyrex™ tube, as above.

Alternatively, run just one of these models, and use the findings to discuss how the other two might work.

Now **ask the pupils** to use what has been found from these simulations to discuss which, if any of these geothermal power sources is renewable.

Finally, discuss the proposition, found in many science textbooks, that 'geothermal energy is renewable'.

Teaching notes

Title: Rock power: geothermal power simulation.

Subtitle: Modelling geothermal power sources – renewable or not?

Topic: Using a density can filled with gravel

Figure 2: The geothermal power model 'in action' (photo courtesy of Chris King).

to model different forms of geothermal power source.

Age range of pupils: 14-19 years.

Time needed to complete activity: 15 minutes per run.

Pupil learning outcomes: Pupils can:

- describe the different situations in which geothermal power can be extracted from rocks;
- explain how a density can of hot gravel can be used to model these forms of geothermal power;
- discuss whether or not these forms of geothermal power can be regarded as renewable.

Context:

These simulations clearly show that:

- 'hot dry rocks' geothermal power is not renewable, since the temperature of the gravel steadily falls as heat is extracted by the overflowing water, so that the temperature of the overflowing water also falls, over time. This is because the heat is extracted much more quickly than it is being gener-

ated by radioactive decay in the rock.

- **'hot wet rocks'** geothermal power is not renewable because it taps into 'fossil heat' accumulated over recent geological time, as a rate much faster than it is being accumulated.
- **'hydrothermal power'** can be extracted renewably, if heat is removed at a slower rate than it is accumulating from the heat source below. However, most hydrothermal power stations extract heat more quickly than it is accumulated, so they only have a finite life and will eventually close. In these cases, heat is being extracted at non-renewable rates.

Note: You can do the first demonstration just by pretending the density can has been heated, by touching it and pretending to burn your fingers – whole classes have been convinced by this!

A fourth source of power, which is sometimes described as 'geothermal', is **'ground source heat pumps'** where water from an underground or surface source has its heat extracted for warming buildings and is recycled. However, since some 98% of the power in these systems comes from solar heating of the Earth's surface, and only around 2% is true geothermal power from the Earth, this is not geothermal power in the sense described above. Air-source heat pumps are also available, where heat is extracted from the air, rather than from the ground.

Following up the activity:

Ask pupils to research how 'ground source heat pumps' work, and whether or

not this power source can be described as 'renewable'. It can, since heat can only be extracted at the same rate as it accumulates.

Underlying principles:

- The Earth generates heat, called geothermal heat.
- The Earth's heat is generated by radioactive decay in the rocks of the Earth (with a component of original heat from the formation of the Earth).
- Earth's heat flows to the surface and can be tapped through the three forms of geothermal power, described above.
- Such power is usually not renewable, because the heat is normally extracted at a faster rate than it accumulates.

Thinking skill development:

If one run of the activity is carried out, and pupils are asked to use this to discuss how the set-up might behave in the two other circumstances, they will use the mental 'construction' of one model and apply it to the two other models. This will provoke pupils into considering and re-working their pre-conceived ideas of how geothermal power is generated. Discussions around the models, and their links with reality, involve more powerful knowledge of the principles and processes. Linking each model with its 'real world' operation develops a greater awareness of how geothermal power works in different geological contexts.

Resource list:

- a large density or displacement can (density cans are also called 'Eureka cans' because they are designed to use

the Archimedes method of measuring density)

- permeable coarse gravel to fill the can to above spout level
- a Perspex™ tube long enough to penetrate nearly to the bottom of the gravel, and stick out of the top
- an oven or hot plate (a hot plate is needed for the 'hydrothermal power' simulation)
- heat-proof mitts or gloves to be used in moving the hot container
- a thermometer or temperature probe to go in the gravel (reading to higher than 100 oC in case the can is heated to over 100 oC)
- containers to catch the overflow (e.g. several measuring cylinders)
- a thermometer to go in the overflow containers
- a sink or basin
- a source of flowing water

Useful Links:

Earthlearningidea: 'Power through the window: which power source might be built in the view you can see from your window?'

Source:

The model was described by Adrian Cook in the Earth Science Teachers' Association's 'Science of the Earth', 'Rock power! – geothermal energy resources' unit (1991), published by Geo Supplies, Sheffield. It was based on an activity originally described in 'Introducing Earth Science' by James Bradbury (1986) published by Blackwell, who gave permission for its use.

References

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